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The Predictors of Body Image Dissatisfaction among Undergraduate Students at the United States International University-Africa, Nairobi, Kenya

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Abstract

Utilizing a sample of 114 undergraduate students studying at the United States International University-Africa, this study analyzed the factors that impacted on body image dissatisfaction among young adults in Kenya. A quantitative design was utilized for the study. Data were collected through a self-administered structured questionnaire and analyzed utilizing the SPSS software version 24 with beta (β) coefficients as the main test statistic. The results showed that those studied had low levels of both body image consciousness and dissatisfaction and that, overall, they were free from the negative consequences of body image dissatisfaction. Regression analysis revealed that further showed that only 4 of 8 individual factors, none of the socio-cultural factors and only 1 of 4 control variables evaluated were significant predictors of body image dissatisfaction. The regression model explained 72.1 percent of the variance in body image dissatisfaction. It was concluded that, among others, the factors that have been utilized as predictors of body image dissatisfaction in Western countries also apply to the Kenyan situation.

Keywords: Body image, body image dissatisfaction, body image consciousness, individual factors, socio-cultural factors

1. INTRODUCTION

Over the years, people have given a lot of importance to the beauty associated with the human body, and hence the term body image. The term refers to an individual's perceptions, beliefs, and emotional and cognitive attitudes regarding their body (Klaczynski, Goold & Mudray, 2004; Sloan, 2003; Stice & Whitenton, 2002). Body image is a reflection of how a person feels concerning whether their body is attractive and appealing based on personal perceptions.

The concept is multidimensional and includes various components, which are behavioral, cognitive, affective and perceptual. Whereas the behavioral dimension refers to what a person does with regards to his or her body, the cognitive aspect deals with the beliefs and thoughts a person has concerning their body. The affective facet, on the other hand, focuses on the feelings a person has concerning their body. Lastly, the perceptual element deals with the way in which a person views himself or herself.

To gauge body image, society has come up with a set of standards that do not always correspond to an individual's perception concerning their body. Some of the standards include being thin, curvy and even having a proportionate body (Waldman, Loomes, Mountford & Tchanturia, 2013). Both women and men have their concerns regarding how they fit society's provided conception of body image. A positive body image occurs when an individual feels good and accepts all aspects of their body (Menzel & Levine, 2011). An individual who has the positive body image tends to be proud of his/her body even in situations where factors such as the media and family ideals may not match up with the individual's appearance (Champion & Furnham, 1999). S/he appreciates and celebrates the natural shape of the body, and understands that his/her physical appearance does not dictate his/her value and character. In addition, the individual will be accepting and proud of the fact that they have a unique body (Kotanski, et al., 2004; Menzel & Levine, 2011). By being confident and comfortable about his/her body, such a person is unlikely to become involved in spending unnecessary time thinking about calories, weight, and food. On the contrary, a negative body image exists whenever an individual feels that his/her body is not able to match up to some expectations such as media, social, and family ideals (Champion & Furnham, 1999; Kotanski, Fisher & Gullone, 2004). An individual who has a negative view of his/her physical appearance and body, experiences dissatisfaction with his/her body image (*Derenne & Beresin, 2006*).

Since the 1950s, many empirical researches have been conducted providing more information about the issue of body image (Kotanski, Fisher & Gullone, 2004; Stice, Maxfield & Wells, 2003). Whereas the physical schema or perceived feelings of the individual's physical appearance may play a major role in the individual's body image (Kotanski, et al., 2004; Schilder, 1950), the predictors of body image dissatisfaction are many and varied. These can be categorized into individual factors and socio-cultural factors. Individual factors include body size, personality traits, depression, or low self-esteem, gender and age (Rothblum, 1992). On the other hand, socio-cultural factors include influences from the family, peer influences, and media influences (Menzel & Levine, 2011; Stice, Maxfield & Wells, 2003).

Negative body image and consequently, dissatisfaction with one's body image has been associated with a number of illnesses and disorders that include eating disorders, body dysmorphic disorder, depression, anxiety, and low self-esteem. Various authors (Birbeck, 2003; Davison & McCabe, 2006; Vonderen and Kinnally, 2012). Vonderen and Kinnally (2012), for example, established that self-esteem and peer comparisons could make the individual develop eating disorders. On the contrary, individuals who experience the body image satisfaction tend to have healthy behaviors and outlook, self-acceptance, and higher self-esteem levels.

The purpose of this study is to explore for the predictors of body image dissatisfaction among undergraduate university students at the United States International University-Africa (USIU-Africa). Doing so is important because the adverse effects of body image dissatisfaction, such as anorexia nervosa and bulimia nervosa (McCabe & Ricciardelli, 2005; Menzel & Levine, 2011), are well documented, especially in Western countries. In Kenya, concerns with body image are catching up, especially among the youth and the middle-aged, as manifested through a variety of ways such as the ever-growing enthusiasm for the gym with maintaining a desirable body type as one of the key objectives, dieting practices and dressing styles among both females and males, and the application of make-up especially among females. In an attempt to further improve and have a positive body image, Kenyan men and women are also doing other useful activities, including engaging in meditation, having an adequate sleep as well as having a daily routine for moisturizing, toning as well as cleansing (Waswa, 2011).

The study is anchored on two specific objectives; to measure the level of body image dissatisfaction, and to test for the effects of established individual and socio-cultural factors on body image dissatisfaction among undergraduate students at USIU-Africa. Through the study, we hope to contribute new knowledge that will increase the understanding of the subject matter of body image in general and the predictors of body image dissatisfaction in particular within the Kenyan context. This is important in light of the fact that much of the research conducted in this subject area focuses on the industrialized nations of the West (see, e.g., Kotanski, Fisher & Gullone, 2004; Schilder, 1950) leaving the Kenyan context understudied.

2. DELINEATION OF STUDY VARIABLES

In all, 15 variables were evaluated as factors impacting on body image dissatisfaction among undergraduate students in USIU-Africa. These included 11 substantive variables and four (4) control variables. The substantive variables, drawn from the existing literature, were grouped into two categories; individual factors and socio-cultural factors. It is to the operational definitions of these that we now turn, commencing with individual factors.

2.1 Individual Factors

Individual factors include personality traits (such as openness, conscientiousness, agreeableness, extraversion, and neuroticism); depression, and low self-esteem (Rothblum, 1990). It has been argued that an individual's personality traits can lead to body image dissatisfaction. Furthermore, individuals who experience depression and low-self-esteem will most likely have a negative view concerning their bodies (Kotanski, et al., 2004). This is especially the case among individuals who have perfectionist tendencies, and those trying to obtain approval from other people. These are likely to develop negative body image perception since they are seeking to become the best when compared to other people (Kotanski, et al., 2004). For the purpose of this study, the following eight (8) individual factors were analyzed: Openness, conscientiousness, agreeableness, extraversion, and neuroticism, depression, (low) self-esteem, and life satisfaction.

The term *openness* is defined after John & Srivastava (1999) to represent the complexity and depth of a person to engage in new experiences. According to them, the individual who is open to new experiences is willing to think outside of the box, is vulnerable as well as willing to try out something new. In this study, it is argued that openness increases the individual's propensity of experiencing body image dissatisfaction.

John and Srivastava (1999) have defined the term *conscientiousness* as a trait that is characterized by being effective at organizing and planning and working within the established rules. As utilized in this study, the term refers to the tendency by an individual to act in a manner that is socially acceptable and also to be able to control his or her impulses. In turn, the person can benefit from achieving their goals. We hypothesize that conscientiousness increases the individual's inclination toward body image dissatisfaction.

For the purpose of this study, the term *agreeableness* refers to the extent to which an individual is able to agree with other people. The term denotes the individual's ability to interact with others. We argue that being agreeable reduces the individual's susceptibility to body image dissatisfaction.

Extroversion refers to the high end of a spectrum whereby a person draws energy from other people. An extrovert recharges his/her energy from other people. A person who has the extroversion trait will seek out the opportunities that provide social interaction. S/he can be described as being prone to action, gregarious, and being comfortable around others (Ozer & Benet-Martinez, 2006). In this study, it is hypothesized that extroversion decreases the individual's predisposition toward dissatisfaction with body image.

Neuroticism refers to a characteristic present in an individual who displays negative traits such as having low-esteem, being sad, and anxious. According to Ozer and Benet-Martinez (2006), a neurotic individual is not sure about himself or herself, is self-conscious and easily angered. We argued that being neurotic raises one's chances of experiencing body image dissatisfaction.

The term *depression* refers to experiencing the lack of pleasure or interest in any daily activity. It also includes other symptoms such as recurrent thoughts of suicide, feelings of worthlessness, and significant weight gain or loss (American Psychological Association, 2017). It is hypothesized here that depression increases one's proclivity towards body image dissatisfaction.

The term *self-esteem* refers to the feelings and beliefs that an individual holds concerning themselves. It is usually formed from other people's perceptions and internal perceptions. The self-worth of the individual is an important factor in determining self-esteem (Roy & Andrews, 1999). In this study, it is argued that individuals with low self-esteem have a higher predisposition toward body image dissatisfaction.

Finally, the term *life satisfaction* denotes the quality of life that an individual is experiencing or subjective well-being. Diener, Emmons, Larsen, & Griffin (1985) define it as the individual's judgment and conclusion concerning their entire life. Individuals who report being satisfied with life are likely to have a positive body image because they believe that

their life has a positive impact on their body. It is hypothesized here that life satisfaction decreases one's likelihood of suffering from body image dissatisfaction.

2.2 Socio-Cultural Factors

The second category of variables evaluated for this study included three (3) socio-cultural factors as follows: Media influences, parental influences, and peer influences. *Media influences* refer to the effect of exposure to media channels such as television, magazines, and the internet on the individual's evaluation of his/her body image. The exposure can have an impact on the perception a person has concerning their body (Grieve & Bonneau-Kaya, 2007). It is hypothesized that the greater the media exposure, the higher the likelihood of experiencing body image dissatisfaction.

As utilized in this study, the term *parental influences* refer the extent to which values espoused by parents determine how one constructs one's body image. By parent, we mean the individual's blood father and mother. We argue that parents tend to have certain values that are shared among the members of the family, which can influence an individual's evaluation of his/her body image. As such, exposure to parental influences is hypothesized to increase the individual's predilection toward body image dissatisfaction.

The term *peer influences* are utilized to refer to the peers' conversations that are held concerning weight, appearance, and even teasing. Such conversations have an influence on the overall perception an individual will have about his/her body (Jones et al., 2004). Consequently, the greater the peer influence, the greater the body image dissatisfaction.

2.3 Control Variables

The following were analyzed as control variables: Perceptions about aging, religious affiliation, complexion, and body weight. As utilized in this study, the term *perception about aging* represents the opinions and views that people hold regarding aging. The perception held by an individual tends to affect how the individual feels about his or her body. We hypothesize that individuals who have a negative view of aging are likely to experience body image dissatisfaction. On the other hand, the term *religious affiliation* denotes the religious faith that an individual abides by. We argue that the teachings presented in a certain religion can influence how the individual engages in activities that can affect their body as well as body image.

As utilized in this study, the term *complexion* refers to the pigmentation of one's skin. Broadly defined, individuals can be classified as dark skinned or light skinned. It is individuals who are light skinned who are considered in this study to be more susceptible to body image dissatisfaction. Finally, *body weight* is used to refer to the individual's objective heaviness of his/her body, measured in kilograms. We argue that persons who have hefty bodies are more likely to experience body image dissatisfaction compared to those who are light bodied.

2.4 Independent Variable

The independent variable for this study is *body image dissatisfaction*. It refers to the individual's negative subjective evaluations of his/her whole body or some parts of it such as legs, stomach, and hips (Stice & Whitenton, 2002).

3. METHODOLOGY

The study was conducted among undergraduate students registered for various degree programs at the United States International University-Africa (USIU-A). The USIU-A is a private non-profit institution located in the Kasarani area of Nairobi, Kenya, behind Safari Park Hotel, off the Thika Superhighway. Established in 1969 as the first private, secular university to operate in Kenya, following an agreement between the trustees of USIU in San Diego, California and the Kenyan Ministry of Education, the university has grown to become one of the largest private universities in the East African region. It is dually accredited by the Commission for University Education (CUE) in Kenya and the Western Association of Schools and Colleges (WASC) in the United States of America (USA). By January 2017, its student population stood at 6960; 5 281 undergraduate students (77.9 percent) and 1 679 graduate students (22.1 percent). The university is organized into four schools as follows - The School of Humanities and Social sciences, the Chandaria School of Business, the School of Science and Technology, and the School of Pharmacy and Health Sciences – offering varied undergraduate and graduate degree programs.

A quantitative research design was utilized for this study. Data were collected utilizing the survey methods. Specifically, self-administered structured questionnaires were utilized. In addition to adducing information related to the socio-economic and demographic characteristics of respondents, the questionnaire sought to establish the respondents' views about the following issues: The level of body image dissatisfaction; perceived positive and negative consequences of body image evaluations, and the effects of individual, cultural and societal factors on body image dissatisfaction. Those administered with the structured questionnaires were selected in three stages. In the first stage, the university was stratified into schools out of which two schools - School of Humanities and Social Sciences and Chandaria School of Business – were randomly selected to be included in the study. The second stage of the sampling process involved the random selection of specific programs offered by each school from which respondents were finally drawn. From the school of Humanities and Social Sciences, the Psychology and International Relations programs were selected, while from the Chandaria School Business it is the International Business Administration and the Finance programs that were sampled. The final stage of the sampling process entailed the selection of the students to be interviewed in each of the four programs selected above. Unlike in earlier stages where random sampling was used, here convenient (availability) sampling was utilized. That is, for each program, a class that was in session during the time when the researcher was available to conduct the interviews was selected and visited. This process went on until the desired sample of 50 students from each school was met.

Data were analyzed utilizing the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) IBM version 24. The analysis occurred in two stages. In the first stage, descriptive statistics (means, standard deviations, frequencies and relative frequencies) was employed. These were utilized to profile the socio-economic and demographic characteristics of the study sample as well as the main patterns emerging from the data. The second stage involved the use of multiple linear regression analysis, with beta coefficient (β) as the test statistic, to test for the effects of various factors on body image dissatisfaction.

4. RESULTS

A total of 114 undergraduate students studying for varying degrees in the United States International University-Africa (USIU-A) were interviewed for this study. Out of this number, 39 (32.2 percent) were males while the rest 75 (65.8 percent) were females. Those interviewed ranged in age from 18-28 years. The mean age was 21.0 years with a standard deviation of 1.97 years. The median age was 21.0 years. As evident from Table 1, those aged under 20 years constituted 19.3 percent of the study sample while those aged between 20 and 24 years comprised 74.6 percent. The remainder 6.1 percents were those aged 25 years and above. Those interviewed included 48.2 percent (55) freshmen, 35.1 percent (40) sophomores, 12.3 percent (14) juniors, and 4.4 percent (5) seniors. Broadly construed, 62.3 percent of them were of light-skinned while the remainder, 37.7 percent were dark skinned. The respondents' body weights ranged from 38 to 95 kilograms; the mean weight was 62.6 kilograms (the standard deviation was 11.0).

Table 1: Distribution of Respondents by Age

Age	Frequency	Percent
18 years	4	3.5
19 years	18	15.8
20 years	31	27.2
21 years	28	24.6
22 years	15	13.2
23 years	8	7.0
24 years	3	2.6
25 + years	7	6.1
Total	114	100.0

The study found that the respondents were characterized by low to moderate levels of body image consciousness. Consistent with this, it was revealed that the interviewees had low levels of body image dissatisfaction. On a scale of 1 to 4, the mean body image dissatisfaction for the six items used to measure body image dissatisfaction was 1.783; the standard deviation was 0.627. Furthermore, low proportions of those interviewed affirmed that they had experienced the negative consequences of body image dissatisfaction, such as eating disorders, unhealthy dieting habits, emotional distress, anxiety, social withdrawal, suicidal thoughts, suicidal acts and unhealthy exercise regimes.

The study had as its core objective ‘to test for the effects of established individual and socio-cultural factors on body image dissatisfaction among undergraduate students at USIU-Africa’. In all, 15 variables were investigated. These included eight (8) individual factors, three (3) socio-cultural factors and four (4) control variables. All individual and socio-cultural factors were measured using multiple indices in which respondents were required to select from strongly disagree (1) to strongly agree (4). The results are presented in Table 2. As evident from the Table, four (4) of the eight (8) individual factors evaluated by the study were found to significantly impact on body image dissatisfaction at the .05 and below the level of significance. These included neuroticism ($\beta = .158$; p-value = .050), depression ($\beta = .443$; p-value = .000), self-esteem ($\beta = .229$; p-value = .002), and life satisfaction ($\beta = -.238$; p-value = .000). This means that undergraduate students who had neurotic personalities were more likely to experience body image dissatisfaction, and so were their counterparts who suffered from depression. Similarly, the results showed that students who had low self-esteem were significantly more likely to exude body image dissatisfaction relative to their counterparts who had high self-esteem. Finally, the study revealed that high levels of life satisfaction tended to significantly lower body image dissatisfaction among those studied. The other four individual factors – openness, conscientiousness, agreeableness, and extraversion – were not found to significantly impact on body image dissatisfaction.

Table 2: Factors Affecting Body Image Dissatisfaction

Factors	Beta (β) Value	P- Value
Individual Factors:		
Openness:	.019	.784
Conscientiousness	-.075	.265
Agreeableness	.025	.673
Extraversion	-.090	.134
Neuroticism	.158	.050
Depression	.443	.000
Low Self-esteem	.229	.002
Life satisfaction	-.238	.000
Socio-cultural Factors:		
Media Influences	-.045	.475
Parental Influences	.103	.149
Peer Influences	-.061	.345
Control Variables:		
Perception about Aging	.046	.437
Religious Affiliation	.061	.263
Complexion	-.120	.038
Body Weight	-.094	.093
		R^2 value = .712

Of the three socio-cultural factors analyzed – that is, media influences, parental influences and peer influences - none was found to significantly impact on body image dissatisfaction. On the other hand, only one (1) of the control variables evaluated - complexion ($\beta = -.120$; p-value = .038) - was shown to significantly impact on body image dissatisfaction at the .05 and

below the level of significance. The results revealed that dark-skinned undergraduate students at USIU-Africa were less likely to experience body image dissatisfaction compared to their light-skinned counterparts. The control variables 'perception about aging', 'religious affiliation,' and 'body weight' were not found to significantly impact on body imager dissatisfaction.

The explained variance (R^2) in body image dissatisfaction was .712. This can be interpreted to mean that of all the factors (independent variables) that cause variation in body image dissatisfaction (the dependent variable), the factors (or variables) analyzed accounted for 71.2 percent.

5. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

The overall aim of this study was to explore for the predictors of body image dissatisfaction among undergraduate students at the United States International University-Africa (USIU-Africa). The study produced some unique findings that require further treatment. First, the study revealed that those interviewed had low levels of both body image consciousness and body image dissatisfaction. This is inconsistent with findings in the West, which have tended to reveal high levels of body image consciousness (Champion and Furnham, 1999; Derenne & Beresin, 2006; Waldman, et al., 2013). There are two possible explanations for this finding. First, the finding could be a manifestation of the fact that despite the permeation of Western culture in Kenya, certain aspects of African culture, in this case, the social construction of the body in general and of body image/beauty in particular, remain strong/ have not been eclipsed by Western construction of the same. This means that individual's perceptions, beliefs, and emotional and cognitive attitudes regarding the body are yet to be fully westernized.

The alternative explanation of the low body image consciousness realized by this study has to do with the nature of the campus environment in Kenya. A closer look at the campus environment in Kenya paints it as a less formal one where most students do not worry much about dressing and appearances. It is the place for casual wear such as jeans/ slacks, t-shirts and other forms of informal wear. Logically, in such an environment, students are less likely to be conscious about their body image; meaning that their individual perceptions, beliefs, and emotional and cognitive attitudes regarding the body are likely to be deliberately suppressed.

The third and final possible explanation of the above findings rests with the composition of the study sample. Whereas those interviewed cut across all years of study, - freshman, and sophomore, junior and senior – the majority of them (62.3 percent) were in their freshman and sophomore years. Logically, juniors and seniors who are approaching graduation and eventual entry into the labor market are more likely to be body image conscious, and consequently to experience body image dissatisfaction. Being older, they are also more likely to have increased sensitivity to physical appearances and body image.

Consistent with the low body image consciousness realized by this study, the results revealed that USIU-Africa's undergraduate students had low/ average levels of body image dissatisfaction, which was the outcome variable for the study. On a scale of 1 to 4, the mean

body image dissatisfaction was 1.783 with a standard deviation of 0.627. This is contrary to results realized by studies conducted in Western countries, which have tended to suggest the prevalence of body image dissatisfaction, especially among young adults, including among university students (see e.g., Ansari et al, 2014; Ferrari et al, 2013; Goswami, Sachdeva and Sachdeva, 2012). It should be noted that the existence of low levels of body image dissatisfaction adduced by this study is backed up by the absence of the symptoms of negative body image consequences - such as attempted suicide, suicide thoughts, withdrawal from friends/peers/colleagues, and eating disorders - among the bulk of those who were interviewed for the study. To reiterate, only 4.5 percent, and 18.0 percent, 9.9 percent, and 11.4 percent of the respondents, respectively agreed that they had attempted suicide, they sometimes entertained suicidal thoughts, their body often forced them to socially withdraw from friends/peers/colleagues, and that they experienced eating disorders because of their body.

The existence of low levels of body image dissatisfaction among those interviewed for this study suggests that the respondents were characterized by positive as opposed to negative body image. Consequently, they viewed their bodies, including the different parts of the same, in a realistic and objective manner, leading them to appreciate and celebrate, as opposed to being ashamed of and condemning the natural shape of their bodies. This is consistent with the literature, which posits that individuals with positive body image appreciate and accept their bodies, and are proud of the fact that they have a unique body (see Kostanski, Fisher and Gullone, 2004). According to Kostanski, et al (2004), such persons are confident and comfortable about their body and, therefore, are unlikely to spend time thinking about calories, body weight, and food.

Regression analysis results revealed that only five (5) of the 15 substantive and control variables analyzed significantly impacted on body image dissatisfaction. Specifically, it was found that undergraduate students characterized by neurotic personalities, depression, and low self-esteem were significantly more likely to suffer body image dissatisfaction, whereas those characterized by high levels of life satisfaction exuded lowered body image dissatisfaction. These results are supported by the existing literature (see e.g., Kostanski, et al., 2004; Rothblum, 1990). In addition, it was revealed that individuals who were dark skinned were significantly less likely to experience body image dissatisfaction. This finding is consistent with expectations. Normally, light-skinned persons are more concerned about their appearance in particular and their body image in general. It is often the case that being light skinned especially among women, is associated with being beautiful. Hence the common saying that 'every man desires to marry or have a light-skinned woman.'

It is noticeable that a large number of the variables, in fact 10 out of 15, analyzed did not impact on body image dissatisfaction significantly. There are a number of possible explanations for this. First, it is possible that these were not important factors among those studied. Second, one may view this situation in terms of the sampling method utilized, especially to select the actual respondents for the study. Relying on convenient/availability sampling at the third stage of the sampling process most probably led to a sample that was not representative. This is likely to have introduced biases as well as increased the sampling error,

thereby impacting negatively on the results of the regression analysis. In this regard, one must reiterate that 62.3 percent of the study sample were in their freshman and sophomore years. Yet, as argued earlier, it is students who are approaching graduation and subsequent entry into the labor market who are more likely to worry about their grooming/body image.

Based on the results of this study, it may be concluded that, contrary to their counterparts in Western countries, undergraduate students at USIU-Africa have low body image consciousness/awareness as well as body image dissatisfaction. However, the factors that have been used to predict body image dissatisfaction by studies conducted in Western countries are also tenable in the Kenyan situation. Their relevance is evident through the explained variances obtained by this study. To reiterate, the regression equations accounted for 72.1 percent of the variance in body image dissatisfaction. Nevertheless, there is a need for further research in Kenya. The research should key on two categories of young adults. First, those who are attending colleges and/or universities throughout the country should be included. In this regard, studies should be conducted covering more private universities as well as bringing in the public sector of higher education. Kenya has a large number of private universities, many of them with a religious inclination. It would be useful to assess whether the construction of body image in general and of beauty, in particular, may vary across students studying in secular and religious inclined private universities. This is important instead of the fact that some of the universities with a religious inclination have a prescribed dressing code.

The second category of young adults that could be the locus of future investigation is the working/career category. This includes those who are aged 25-45 years, who have completed college/university and are pursuing career paths in the labor market. It is posited here that it is this category of young adults who might have embraced formality in dressing, and are very conscious of their appearances because it is part of their organizational/workplace culture. Of course, it is this same group of young adults who are likely to exude higher levels of body image consciousness as well as to experience body image dissatisfaction where individual/other expectations and set standards are not met. Not to forget that this category of young adults has the financial capability to maintain/ sponsor a preferred body image.

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